

PROBLEMS IN TEACHING KARAKALPAK PHRASEOLOGY AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the main problems encountered in the process of teaching Karakalpak phraseology and ways to overcome them. The text highlights such problems as the inability of students to actively use phraseological units in speech, the lack of harmony between theoretical knowledge and practice, low motivation, and the lack of textbooks and materials. Also, methods for effectively solving these problems through interactive methods, a creative approach, information and communication technologies, and increasing motivation are shown.

In Karakalpak language lessons, the study of phraseological units - phrases, proverbs, explanatory expressions, and idiomatic sentences - is important for increasing the vocabulary of students, developing their speech culture, and forming their artistic thinking. However, in the process of teaching phraseology, a number of problems arise, the solution of which is an important task.

Problems: Passivity in speech.

Many students, despite knowing phraseological units, cannot actively use them in their speech. This reduces the ability to apply phraseological richness in practice.

The discrepancy between theoretical knowledge and practice.

In lessons, phraseological units are often explained theoretically, but insufficient attention is paid to their use in spoken and written language.

Low student motivation.

Since the study of phraseology is often associated with difficult and dry exercises, students lose interest in the lesson.

Insufficient textbooks and teaching materials.

Some textbooks lack materials that allow for the study of phraseological units with practical exercises.

Ways to solve problems:

Use of interactive methods.

Through such methods as "role-playing games", "discussion", "cluster", and "brainstorming", students learn to use phraseological units in context. For example, the use of proverbs or phrases in accordance with the situation ensures their stable use in speech.

Implementation of a creative approach.

By assigning students the task of writing short stories, essays, or dialogues based on phraseological units, their creative thinking is developed.

Use of information and communication technologies.

Multimedia presentations, electronic textbooks, and interactive tests help to visually explain the meaning and use of phraseological units.

Increasing motivation.

To increase students' interest, it is effective to organize games, quizzes, word games, and group activities.

Methods of working with text.

Analyzing phraseological units using methods such as Insert and Venn diagrams and placing them in the text develops students' analytical and practical skills.

The elimination of problems in teaching Karakalpak phraseology is carried out through interactive methods, a creative approach, information and communication technologies, and increasing motivation. These approaches strengthen students' phraseological richness, enhance their speech competence, and increase their interest in language.

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